

THE REDUCED SMARANDACHE SQUARE-DIGITAL SUBSEQUENCE IS INFINITE

Maohua Le

Abstract . In this paper we prove that the reduced Smarandache square-digital subsequence is infinite.

Key words. reduced Smarandache square-digital subsequence, infinite.

Form all square integers $0, 1, 4, 9, 16, 25, 36, \dots$, we choose only the terms whose digits are all perfect squares and disregarding the square numbers of the form $N \cdot 10^{2t}$, where N is also a square number and t is a positive integer. Such sequence is called the reduced Smarandache square-digital subsequence . Bencze [1] and Smith [2] independently proposed the following question.

Question . How many terms in the reduced Smarandache square-digital subsequence?

In this paper we completely solve the mentioned question . We prove the following result.

Theorem . The reduced Smarandache square-digital subsequence has infinitely many terms.

By our theorem , we can give the following corollary immediately .

Corollary . The reduced Smarandache square-partial-digital subsequence has infinitely many terms.

Proof of Theorem . For any positive integer n , let

$$(1) \quad A(n) = 2 \cdot 10^n + 1.$$

Then we have

$$(2) (A(n))^2 = 4.102^n + 4.10^n + 1 = 4 \underbrace{0 \cdots 0}_{(n-1)\text{zeros}} 4 \underbrace{0 \cdots 0}_{(n-1)\text{zeros}} 1.$$

By (1) and (2), we see that $(A(n))^2$ belongs to the reduced Smarandache square—digital subsequence for any n thus, the sequence has infinitely many terms. The theorem is proved.

References

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Department of Mathematics
 Zhanjiang Normal College
 Zhanjiang, Guangdong
 P R CHINA